

THE STUDY OF HISTORY, RELIGION, CULTURE OF SOUTH, SOUTH-EAST AND EAST ASIA IN UZBEKISTAN

Nizomiddinov N.G.

Professor, Doctor of Historical Sciences, UNESCO Chairman on the Comparative Study of World Religions and Religious Studies of International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14706486>

Abstract. *The collection of ten books is the continuation of the subject of investigation of the great Uzbek scientist of X-XI (973-1048) centuries Abu Raykhan Beryni in the years of Independence of Uzbekistan. Shortly speaking, the creating of collection of seven books in Uzbekistan is the logic continuation of the subject of investigation of the great Uzbek scientist of X-XI (973-1048) centuries Abu Raykhan Beruni, who over a thousand years ago was the author of the scientific method of comparative study of the world national values – history, religions, culture and traditions.*

Keywords: *history, religions, culture and traditions.*

The study of above-mentioned subject on the basis of national mentality is an initial step in the years of Independence. Because, such a positive approach to the sources of spiritual values, if on the one hand, helps to feel initial oneness of mankind noted in divine messages [1]; on the other hand, it creates mutual understanding among the nations with different faiths, which is important today in struggling against the international extremism and terrorism. By the way, «All religions, - as a well-known sufi Mansoor Khallaj said, - are the different twigs of one and the same Tree». In accordance with this view-point, in our investigations we tried to continue the tradition of Abu Reikhan Beruni, who over a thousand years ago created the scientific method of comparative study of the world national values – history, religions, culture and traditions.

The present study divided into nine books:

1. The first book is dedicated to the history, religion and culture of India, Shri Lanca, Nepal and Bhutan.

2. The second book dedicated to the history, religion and culture of Indonesia, Malaysia, Vietnam, Burma, Thailand, Cambodia, Laos, Singapore and Philippines.

3. The third book dedicated to the history, religion and culture of China and Tibet.

4. The fourth book dedicated to the history, religion and culture of Korea and Japan.

5. The fifth book dedicated to the translation of the religious-philosophic teachings and historical manuscripts of South, South-East and East Asia into Uzbek language.

6. The sixth book dedicated to the history of Islam in South, South-East and East Asia.

7. The seventh book dedicated to the Literature, Culture and Science of South, South-East and East Asia

8. The eighth book dedicated to the history of historical relations of the Central Asia with the countries of South and East Asia.

9. The ninth book dedicated to the collection of articles regarding the history, religion and culture – Literature, Music, Architecture and Miniature of South, South-East and East Asia.

Below we decided to give short information about the scientific structure of the study from each book separately.

I. «The Ancient History, Religion and Culture of South Asian peoples» (India, Shri Lanca, Nepal, Bhutan)

1. The main ancient factors of the history of India is the migration of Aryans.
2. The history of the rise of Magatha, Nanda, Maurya, Kushan, Gupta dynasty empires and southern kingdoms as: Pallava, Vakataka, Panda and Chola.
3. The description of Indian religious-philosophic teachings: Veda, Brahmanism, Jainism, Buddhism, Yoga-shastr, Hinduism, Bhaktism and Sikhism.
4. Invasion of Muslim rulers from the south and north of India and the reasons of acceptance Islam in India.
5. The monoteistic ideas of Hinduism and their similar points with Islam.
6. The history of ancient Indian culture, its role and significance in the treasure of values of mankind
7. Creation and prosperity of «Indo-Muslim culture» in all spheres of life: architecture, painting, music, art and literature in Brajbhasha, Hindi, Urdu, Persian and Turkic languages.

Moreover, the present book includes the history, religions and culture of Shri Lanka, Nepal and Bhutan, because the peoples all above mentioned countries had close relationship with India from the ancient times.

In order to imagine the methods of investigation of the chosen subject at the end of each structure short quote will be given related to history, religion or culture as below:

«For example, Indian philosophical thought about the logical sense of all periods of the world existence – the past, present and future – from its creation up to the end. And this process, according to the interpretation of Hinduism, having reached its last destination, reverts back to the initial position and starts again. In other words, the creativeness of God is just like His qualities, constant and forever. Therefore, the doctrine of rebirth conception is explained as the law of eternity of the life circulation, according to which everybody is regarded as a particular presence of Brahma - God's first creation.

Now we would like to underline similar ideas of Hinduism and Islam in short:

1.«The creation and qualities of Brahma» can be seen in the following lines of «Zubdatul-Khaqayiq» (Cream of the Truth) written by Aziziddin Nasafi: «Initially Allah created Javkhar (Ruh-i avval), i.e. the initial soul».

2. In «Bhagavat-Gita» Shri Krishna said: «Men, who are born again and again, cannot come near to Me and at the end they obtain the lower forms of life». It is clear from this precept that the demons in each birth as a seed of their heredity keep falling down unless they enter in the body of animals. In fact, the incarnation of soul in different forms of existence is also observed in Sufism:

«He, who does not trust in God and recognize the Prophet and commits sins, there is no way for such people in the world of Truth – the upper destination of pure people».

3. In Hinduism «People are generally defined as a small Ishvar», and in Islam, as Ibn Arabi describes: «People are small space like «Al-a'lam» «Al-mukhtasar - Small world».

In terms of the history of Islam in India, a question may arise: what was the impact of Islam on the Indian life, education and art? Some Indian scholars, historians and religious thinkers believe that Islam had a huge influence and in many ways enriched the Indian culture and art by creating new institutions. But at the same time, among the invaders who came from the south and north were many scientists and Sufi saints impressed by what they saw in the country. For example,

Arab scholar al-Jahiz in his diary left very important information regarding the Indian medicine, astrology, philosophy, mathematics, literature and music.

Al-Beruni had a good command of Sanskrit and was the first to translate «Sankhya» and «Jogasutra» into the Arabic language, including «Almagest» and «Elements» from Greek into Sanskrit for Indians. As centuries elapsed, Iranian scholar of the 12th century Abdul Karim Shahrastani wrote: Indian people became «Umma kabira wa millati azimat - Great nation and religious community». Likewise, Mahatma Gandhi emphasizes, «Hindus and Muslims of India are two nations that God made one and man will never be able to drive them apart».

II. «The Ancient History, Religion and Culture of South-East Asian peoples» (Indonesia, Malaysia, Vietnam, Burma, Thailand, Cambodia, Laos, Singapore)

«The History, Religion and Culture of Ancient Indonesia, Malaysia, Vietnam, Burma, Thailand, Cambodia, Laos, Singapore and Philippines»

The present book – designed for the students of higher education helps to study the history of the above mentioned countries. Having taken into consideration the interest of students, the structure of the book has been made up as follows:

1. Pre-history of all presented countries.
2. Main features of their geographic location.
3. The history of formation of local statehood.
4. Short history of Buddhism, Hinduism, Confucianism, Taoism and Islam in South-east Asia.
5. History of culture: oral poetry, classical literature, art of music, dance, architecture, sculpture schools, painting, calligraphy, science, historiography, dressing and needle-work.
6. Their economic potential of all mentioned countries
7. The history of traditions and holidays
8. Chronology of historical periods
9. Brief information about landscapes
10. Glossary

«As a rule before the speaking about the history of Indonesian people, first of all it should be paid attention to the very two difficult problems:

First – the difficulty of the complete explanation of all islands territory which situated separately.

Second – approximately all the cases in islands happened under the outside pressure».

According to the available literature in our hand there are seven directions related with the appearing of Indonesian people in archipelago.

First direction – the ancestors of Indonesians came to archipelago 5000 years before across the Taiwan and Philippines [2].

Second direction – the Indonesian people divided in two ethnic groups: in East Melanesian and in West Austronesian [3]

Third direction – according to archeological information to the territory of the present Indonesia the migration of south-east Asians started from the upper paleolithic period.

Fourth direction – according to the last internet information the migration of mongoloid ethnic groups to the territory of Indonesia was in the second millennium before area. And the migration during the first millennium which brought to Indonesia the high developed culture and agriculture of bronze period were the ancestors of the present Indonesians [5].

Fifth direction – from the remains of austronesians which have been accepted in 1891 in Java, was known, that who came from the (shore) coasts area of China and leaved here more than 150.000 years ago [6].

Sixth direction – the first Melanesians came to the archipelago from the East – from Andaman Islands of the Bay of Bengal and after austronesians came here from West – from China through the Taiwan and Philippines [7]

Seventh direction – «as Indonesian ancient history shows, the ancestors of the present people of archipelago came here 40.000 years ago. They mainly migrated from Malay peninsula, Burma, Thailand, Philippines and other places. After in this area lived immi-grants from different parts of Indian subcontinent and Asian territory. The culture of the immigrants has similar points with primitive culture of the local peoples. As for religion here should be noted, that the religion of immigrants connected with divine powers in the nature was upper then the idea of the local religion»

III. «The Ancient History, Religion and Culture of East Asian peoples» (China, Tibet)

It is not secret that the peoples from ancient times live with the desire to reach the highest level of spiritual and physical perfection regardless of scientific, social and even economic achievements as their ancestors attained. There are so many examples when it comes to ancestor's morality, lifestyle and experience that rose under religious conditions. In this regard, Chinese Confucianism, Taoism and Buddhism can be clear evidence to all the above-mentioned.

However, religious feelings start to change their relation to the world of soul both in form and sense. In other words, for example in China, the acceptance of the Dao teachings as a religion was the proof of awaking of transcendental imagination of the Creator. Moreover, Buddhism discovered for the Chinese believers new spiritual space like 'Nirvana' and the life after death. In spite of this, Confucianism managed to preserve its traditional concepts due to its key elements and essential values.

The same process could also be observed in the history and activity of Buddhism with «Bonpo» in Tibet. As for the history of Islam, in this part of the globe, it is necessary to note that a new religion was initially established mostly by Muslim merchants and partly by local tribes.

It is known that in most scientific works, the religious philosophy of the South and East has been investigated on the basis of moral, social and even administrative respon-sibilities of believers in society. It means that philosophic outlook of religious people should firstly be studied by means of spiritual, social and political life of people in the ancient periods. Only in this case, there might be possibilities to define how these factors obtained religious importance. With this aim, we decided to set the focus on the follo-wing points:

- 1.The geography, history, religious mythology, culture of the ancient China.
- 2.Confucianism, Taoism, and Buddhism as religious and ethnic sources of East Asian peoples.
- 3.Similarities of Buddhism with local philosophical teachings in the countries of Eastern Asia.
- 4.Specification of Chan Buddhism and Lamaism.
- 5.Similarities of Chinese religious doctrines with Islam in the context of spiritual values of mankind.

IV. «The history of Islam in the South, South-East and East Asia (India, Indonesia, Malaysia, China, Korea, Japan)

According to the Korean scientific sources the Neolithic Era began in the peninsula about ten thousand years ago. The Koreans are believed to have settled down there around 4000 B.C. In fact, the Koreans have a long history of 5000 years, which is unquestionably significant part of the world history.

The study of such an ancient and great history is important in order to understand the spiritual similarities of the Korean and Uzbek peoples whose cultural and economic relations are rapidly evolving.

The present research is practically the initial step in the field of investigation of the history, religion and culture of ancient Korea and is consisted of the following parts:

The first part is devoted to the history of the Korean statehood, beginning from the tribal governments to kingdoms and their mutual political, economic and cultural relations.

The second part deals with the history of the Korean religions. Along with religious-philosophic teachings, this part discusses political, social life and development phases of the Korean people.

The third part sheds light on the history of ancient Korean culture with some key factors throughout the years of crises and prosperity.

In a word, during a long history of different events under local empires, the people of Korean peninsula showed national character and moral stability, especially during the battles with foreign countries.

All the above-mentioned parts in the book are divided into the following list of sub-jects:

1. Pre-history of Korean Peninsula.
2. History of Korean migration to peninsula.
3. History of Korean tribal system and its unity.
4. History of Korean religious mythology.
5. History of Korean Confucianism, Korean Taosism, Korean Buddhism and Islam in Korea.
6. History of Korean statehood: Choson, Pejke, Silla – Three kingdoms, Parhai, United Silla, Kougrey and Choson.
7. History of Korean culture: oral poetry, classical literature, art of music, dance, puppet and shadow theatre, architecture, sculpture school, painting, science, historio-graphy.
8. History of Korean dressing, needle-work, gardening and kitchen with detailed description.
9. Chronology of Korean history of statehood.
10. Brief information on Korean landscape.
11. The Korean studies in Uzbekistan.
12. Glossary.
13. Short information about Korean States.

The aim of the book is to study and analyze the Japanese history and society with respect to its ancient culture, traditions and transformations endured for centuries

The first part is devoted to the prehistory of the Japanese and their statehood, beginning from the tribal governments up to the Yamato, Nara, Heian, Fujiwara Regen-cy, Kamakura and Tokugawa periods. In the very part, mutual political, economic and cultural relations are emphasized in terms of diplomacy and shedding light on the reasons of battles among the nations, such as Chinese, Koreans, Mughals and Europeans.

The second part deals with the history of the Japanese religions, as Shinto, including the Japanese Confucianism, Taoism and Buddhism. Along with religious-philosophic teachings, this part discusses politically-social life and development of the Japanese people. It should be noted that at first look, in the Japanese religious history, the above-mentioned foreign religions seem to have easily converted the minds of local people.

The third part sets focus on the history of ancient Japanese culture, where also a brief description is provided about the introduction of Chinese thought and culture. The very publication also acquaints the readers with some key factors of Japanese cultural development throughout the years,

In a word, during a long history of different events under local historical periods, the people of Japan showed the national character and moral stability in every situation, especially during the battles with other countries.

All the parts mentioned above are divided into the following list of subjects:

1. Pre-history of Japanese islands
2. Main features of the country and geographic position
3. History of formation of Japanese tribal-statehood
4. Kokutay is the base of Japanese statehood principles
5. History of Yamato and Asuka periods
6. Taika is a period of greed reforms in Japan
7. History of Nara, Heian, Fujiwara Regency, Kamakura, Taira periods
8. History of periods of Tokugawa Shogunate
9. Shintoism is the national religion of Japanese
10. History of Japanese Zen Buddhism, Taoism, Konfucionism
11. History of Christianity and Islam in Japan
12. Institution of Taiho-era in Nara
13. History of Japanese Culture: oral poetry, classical literature, art of music, dance, puppet theatre, architecture, sculpture schools, painting, calligraphy, science, historio-graphy, dressing, needle-work
14. Short description and translation of 'Kodziki' and 'Ni-hon seki'
15. History of Japanese traditions and holidays
16. Chronology of Japanese historical periods
17. Brief information on the landscape of Japan
18. Studies of Japan in Uzbekistan
19. Glossary
20. Short information about modern Japan in English

V. «The translation of religious-philosophical and historical sources of South, South-East and East Asia

The first of all before the speaking about the subject, it should be noted the decree (24.05.2017) of the President of Uzbekistan SH.M.Mirziyoev about the «Action of perfection of the system of saving, applying and propagandize of ancient manuscripts» which related not only national, but at the same time it concerns to the reserve of man-kind values also. Exactly from this point of view the translation from Sanskrit into Arabic language of Indian philosophic teachings like Sakhya and Patanjaly by Abu Raikhan Beruniy is the proof for positive relation of our ancestors to mankind manuscripts. Because, the translation of historical, religious-philosophy,

statehood, juridical, economic and social resources in Uzbek language it is the logical continuation of the great ancestors' tradition in the years of Independence.

By the way the reason of accentuation of publishing of the chrestomathy is that, the comparable study of religious manuscripts included in official study program of the Academy, but in spite of this not yet sufficient materials for preparing teachers. Moreover, in internet sites all the translation of religious-philosophic teachings in Russian or English language, which are not useful for the students of Uzbek groups. And we think, that, by this reason the presented chrestomathy can be used as study-guide, where available also glossary of terminology together with their translation and actual dates of important historical events.

The above-mentioned information contains following religious-philosophic sources:

Indian religious sources:

Veda

Aitareya brahman

Shapatha brahman

Aranyaki brahman

Meytri upanishad

Kena upanishad

Vaisheshika upanishad

Sri Acaranga sutra

Sri syagadanga sutra

Sri bhangsvati sutra

Vijayapitaka

Sutta-nipata

Dhammapada

Yoga-Shastr

Bhagavad-Gita

Arthshastr

The Laws of Manu

Adi Granth

Chinese religious sources:

Lun yu (Analects)

Dao de Jing (Tao te Ching)

Sima Qian – Record of the Grand History

Chinese Buddhism

Korean sources::

Korean religious mythology

Korean Buddhism

Samguk Sagi

Japanese sources: :

Kojiki

Nihon Shoki

Shoku Nihongi

The Taiho Code

Kokutai

Tayka

VI. «The history of Islam in South, South-East and East Asia

According to the opinion of academician V.V.Bartold «...even when for muslims the political success changed to failure, it was not feeled in the spreading the Islam. And also, the spreading of Islam was not the responsibility of prophet Muhammad. Because in Islam the first time was declared principle which before did not observe in other religion

لَا إِكْرَاهَ فِي الدِّينِ قَدْ تَبَيَّنَ الرُّشْدُ مِنَ الْغَيِّ فَمَنْ يَكْفُرْ بِالطَّاغُوتِ
عَلِيمٌ وَيُؤْمِنُ بِاللَّهِ فَقَدِ اسْتَمْسَكَ بِالْعُرْوَةِ الْوُثْقَىٰ لَا انفصامَ لَهَا وَاللَّهُ سَمِيعٌ

«There is no compulsion in Faith. The correct way has become distinct from the erroneous. Now, whoever rejects the Tāghūt (the Rebel, the Satan) and believes in Allah has a firm grasp on the strongest ring that never breaks. Allah is All-Hearing, All-Knowing» [67. 2:256].

So, if the present translation on the one hand gives the chance to study the history of Islam in these regions were available different local religions, on the other hand, it will give to find-out the understanding of the local people the religious bases of the Islamic philosophy. But wherever Islam came, it has been adopted in the spirit of the local religion. For example the very process could be seen in the Central Asia where in the national ceremonies still remained traditions of Zoroastrianism. By this reason Islam faced with such establishment in all above mentioned regions.

In this case in order to image the condition of Islam in South, Southeast and East Asia should be used the method of «comparable study of world religions» And thanks to the this one can have knowledge about the some similar points of Islam with local religions.

In content of the book given the list of countries, where Islam on geographic bases step by step was adopted.

VII. The history of Literature, Culture and science of South, South-East and East Asia.

The first, about this book should be noted, that where all given information regarding the history of literature, culture and science concerns only to its initial period of the arising of national values of the peoples who live in South, South-East and East regions. Moreover, their treasure of cultural creations recognized by mankind and it even became the subject for scientific investigations.

The relations of Uzbekistan with the all three regions, which in the field of economic progress plays very solid roll throughout the world, has two important lines. If from one side the result of this investigation will give us knowledge about the spiritual world of partners, from other side it helps us to understand their national mentality.

Foreword

The history of Indian literature

The history of Indian music

Indo-Muslim painting culture

The history of Chinese literature

The history of Chinese music culture

The history of Chinese painting culture

The history of Chinese architecture

The history of Chinese science

The history of Korean literature

The of Korean music and song

The history of Korean painting culture
The history of statue culture
The history of Korean architecture
The history of science
The history Japan literature
The history Japan music instruments and duns
Kabuki – Japan theatre culture
The history of Japan painting
The history of statue
The history of Japan architecture
The history of Japan science
The history of Indonesian literature
The history of Indonesian mu sic and duns culture
The history of Indonesian architecture
The history of Malaysian literature
The history of Malaysian music
The history of Malaysian duns
The Malaysian doll and shadow theatre
The history of Malaysian architecture

REFERENCES

1. Куръони карим (Таржима ва изоҳлар муаллифи Алоуддин Мансур). 1992.
2. Абу Рейхан Беруний. Индия. Избранные соч. II том. Т. изд-во АН Узбекистана, 1963.
3. Аш-Шахрастани. Книга о религиях и сектах. Часть 1. (Перевод с арабского С.М.Прозорова) М.: «Ислам», 1984.
4. Ашрафян К.А. Дели: история и культура. М. «Наука», 1987.
5. Авдиев В.И. Қадимги шарқ тарихи.Т. Ўқув-педагогик нашриёти.1956.
6. Александр Мень. История религии: в поисках пути, истины и жизни. М. 2001.
7. Арутюнов С.А., Светлов Г.Е. Старые и новые боги Японии. М. «Наука». Гл. ред. вост. лит. 1968.
8. Афанасий Никитин. Хождение за три моря. М-Л. 1953.
9. Бхагавад-гита(как она есть) Изд-во «Бхакти-веданта Бук Траст» Бомбей.1984.
10. Бартольд В.В. Сочинения VI-т. М. «Наука». 1966.
11. Бартольд В.В. Сочинения II-т.(2ч.) М. «Наука».1964.
12. Бертельс Е.Э. Избранные труды (Суфизм и суфийская литература). М.: «Наука», 1965.
13. Буддийский культовый центр Кара-Тепе в старом Термезе. М. «Наука», 1972.
14. Бонгард-Левин Г.М., Ильин Г.Ф. Древняя Индия. М. «Наука». 1969.
15. Введение в Буддизм. Санкт-Петербург.1999.
16. Васильев Л.С. История религии востока. М. 2000.
17. Древняя Индия: история, язык, культура. М. «Наука» 1982.
18. Дамьен Кеоун. Буддизм. М. изд-во «Весь мир» 2001.
19. Дж. Неру. Взгляд на всемирную историю. 1 том. . «Прогресс». 1977.
20. Древнеиндийская философия. М. Изд-во соц. эконом. лит. 1972.
21. Джеймс В. Многообразие религиозного опыта. (Спб) 1993.

22. Ева Вонг. Даосизм. М. Изд-во «Гранд» 2001.
23. Ермаков Л.К. Культы и верования в раннем периоде японской культуры. (Синто – путь японских богов.) Санкт-Петербург. «Гиперион» I-том. 2002.
24. Жуковский Н.Л. Ламаизм и ранние формы религии. М. «Наука». 1977.
25. Ионова Ю.В. Пережитки тотемизма и религиозных обрядов корейцев (Религия и мифология народов Восточной и Южной Азии) М. 1970.
26. История древнего востока. М.: «Высшая школа»1972.
27. История древнего мира. Ранняя древность. Гл. изд. вост. лит. М.1983.
28. История стран зарубежной Азии в средние века. М. «Наука», 1970.
29. Кочетков А.Н. Буддизм. М. «Наука»,1976.
30. Культура древней Индии. М. «Наука»,1975.
31. Костинский Д.Н. Непал. М. «Госгеографиздат», 1951.
32. Корея. Корейская служба информации для зарубежных стран. Самхва Принтинг Ко. Лтд. Се-ул.2000.
33. Клайв Эррикер. Буддизм. М. 2001.
34. Луния Б.Н. История индийской культуры. М. 1960.
35. Мещериков А.Н. Синтоизм и другие государства (Синто – путь японских богов. Санкт-Петербург «Гиперион» I-том. 2002.).
36. Мещериков А.Н. Синто и буддизм (Санкт-Петербург «Гиперион» I-том. 2002.).
37. Низамутдинов И. Очерки истории культурных связей Средней Азии и Индии в XVI-XIX в. Т. «Фан», 1961.
38. Низамутдинов И. Из истории среднеазиатско-индийских отношений. Т. изд. «Узбекистан». 1969.
39. Низомиддинов Н.Жануби-Шаркий Осиё диний-фалсафий таълимотлари ва ислом. Т. «Фан ва технологиялар марказининг босмахонаси». 2006.
40. Низомиддинов Н. Ҳиндистонда ислом: тарих, ижтимоий-сиёсий ҳаёт ва ҳинд-мусулмон маданияти. Т. 2008.
41. Накорчевский А. Синто. Санкт-Петербург 2002.
42. Низомиддинов.И XVI-XVIII асрларда Ўрта Осиё-Ҳиндистон муносабатлари. Т. «Фан», 196
43. Родионов М.А. Учение друзов в изложении Сами Насиба. (Ислам: религия, общество, государство) М. «Наука»,1984.
44. Радхакришнан. Индийская философия. II-том. М. «Наука»,1956.
45. Степугина Т.В. Китай в первой половине первого тысячелетия до н.э.(История древнего мира: расцвет древних обществ)М. Наука. 1986.
46. Степугина Т.В. Расцвет рабовладельческого общества в Китае (История древнего мира: расцвет древних обществ) М. «Наука». Гл. ред. вост. лит. 1983.
47. Сыма Цянь. Исторические записки. (Перевод с китайского икомментарий Р.В.Вяткина и С. Таскина) М. 1975.
48. Страны и народы востока. Выпуск XIV. М. «Наука». 1972.
49. Ставиский Б.Я. Кушанская бактрия: проб-лемы, история и культура М. «Наука», 1977
50. Струве В.В. История древнего востока. Огиз. Госполитиздат, М.1941
51. Семека Е.С. Структура некоторых цейлонских ритуалов и мифов в связи с культом деревьев. Наука»,1972.

52. Синьцзян, китайская земля: прошлое и настоящее. Синьцзянское народное изд. КНР, Урумчи 2006.
53. Торчинов Е.А. Даосизм. Санкт-петербург. 1998.
54. Торчинов Е.Б. Религии мира. Санкт-Петербург. 2002.
55. Хан В.С. Корейская философия. Ташкентский государственный институт востоковедения. 2004.
56. Хрестоматия по истории древнего востока. М. Изд. «Высшая школа» 1980.
57. Яблоков И.Н. Религиоведение. М. «Гидрарики» 2000.
58. Ahtarul Wasey. Indo-Islamic Cultural Interfase Islam in India. Edited by Asghar Ali Engineer. First published in India 2000).
59. Abdulrayim Gavahi. Mistical Relations between Iran and India (Sufis and Sufism. Edited by Nee-ra Misra. Manohar 2004.
60. Contemporary Relevance of Sufism. Indian council for cultural relations. Published by Himanchal Som. New Delhi 1999.
61. Ch'en E.M. Tao as the Great Mother and In-fluence of Motherly Love in the Shaping of Chinese Philosophy (History of religions. Vol 14. No1) 1974.
62. Ernst C.W. Sufism and Yoga according to Muhammad Ghawth. (Швециядан юборилган мақоланинг ксеро нусхаси).
63. Elliot H.M. The History of India. V-2. 1931.
64. Ghurye G.S. Caste and Class in India. London 1954
65. Gokul Chand Narang. Real Hinduism. New book society. New Delhi 1999.
66. History: Korea, its history and culture. Published by Korean Oversease Information Service. Seoul. 1994.
67. Meditation and jewels of knowledge published by Raja Yoga Centre in Australia for the Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University. Fvount Abu Rajasthan. 1997.
68. James Hewitt. The complete Yoga book. Lon-don 1987.
69. Moreland W. H., Chandra Atul Chaterjee. A history of India. Fourth edition. London 1957.
70. Maksud Ahmad Khan. A Rare Suhrawardy Manuscript of Late Fourteenth Century AD: The «Malfuzal» of Ahaikh Akhi Jamshed Rajgiri (Sufis and Sufism. Edited by Neeru Misra Manohar. 2004).
71. Nilakanta Sastry. A History of South India. 1969.
72. Nizametdinov N.G. The study of Kabir's poetry in Uzbekistan. (The journal of the «Asiatic Society») Culcatta. India. 2001.
73. Islam in India. Edited by Asghar Ali Engineer. First published in India 2000.
74. Olmsted. The History of Persian Empire. Chicago, 1959.
75. James Hewitt. The complete Yoga book. London 1987.
76. Pande B.N. The Vedant and Sufism. A Comparative Study. (Contemporary Relevance of Sufism. Indian council for cultural relations. Published by Himanchal Som. New Delhi 1999).
77. Ramila Thapper. A short history of India. V-1. Penguin book. London. 1966.
78. Sufis and Sufism. Edited by Neeru Misra Ma-nohar. 2004.
79. Sandeep Bagchee. Nad-Understanding Raga Music. Published by «Eshwar». Mumbai, 1998.
80. Thara Chand. Influence of Islam on Indian culture. Allahabad 1963.
81. The Rig Veda. Published by Penguin Books 1981.

82. The Sacred Books of the East. V-XVII. Ox-ford. 1881.
83. The Tarikh-i Rashidi of Muhammad Haidar (Translation of Denison Ross) London. 1895.
84. Warran H.C. Buddhism in translation. Cambrige. 1906.
85. صورتگران و خوشنویسان هرات در عصر تیموران. معلق علی احمد نعیمی. از نشریات انجمن تاریخ افغانستان.
86. مغلیہ عہد. مسلمان و ہندو مورخن کی نظر میں. جلد اول. معارف پریس اعظم گرہ مین چھپی.

